

Analysis of the scripts for the selected health education videos

These are five scripts that the NID team modified based on the health information regarding diabetes, which the author borrowed from Diabetes South Africa (Diabetes SA). The messages shown below are highlighted in different colors to illustrate how the scripts were modified to suit Deaf people's understanding.

The script of Video 1 Brief information about diabetes

New script rearranged during the co-design activity

Now you know about your body and about producing energy. What happens if you have diabetes? Diabetes means that you have a problem in your pancreas. The problem is that the pancreas cannot produce enough insulin. It is trying really hard, but it just cannot produce enough insulin. The body cells are still good. You have enough glucose, but the glucose cannot enter the cells because the pancreas does not produce enough insulin. So you have a lot of glucose but not energy. That is what diabetes is.

Noted:

■ Original script

■ Elaboration= introduction= signalling

■ Elaboration= repetition for emphasis

Figure 1. The script of *Brief information about diabetes*.

The script of Video 2 How the human body gets energy

New script rearranged during the co-design activity

The sign that you are going to see now is about glucose, insulin, and energy for the body—for you to run. How does the body get energy? Our body gets energy so that you can walk, do things, do all kinds of things. **Your body has to have energy where does it come from? You don't have a battery that you can plug in. You don't have electricity that you plug-in, too.** Where do you get your energy from? It is from food. Food gives you energy. So, you are eating food. So the food is in your stomach where it is digested. In the food, there is something called, "glucose." The sign looks like this...Glucose is in your body now. Glucose is incredibly important because that gives you energy. **If you don't have any glucose, you will not have any energy.** The body gets glucose and it spreads throughout the body via the blood. So the blood goes all over your body. And at the same time, you need energy all over your body. **So, if you are signing with one hand, you need energy. If you are blinking, you need energy. You need energy all over. So the glucose is sent all over.** In your blood there is glucose. And there are cells in your body. And glucose is going through your blood. Glucose has to enter into the cells. Then, it can change into energy. **If the glucose is just in the blood, it does not give energy. It has to go inside the cells. The problem is the glucose can't enter the cells by itself. There can be a lot of glucose in the blood, but it can't enter the cells.** It needs insulin. **Insulin is not from food.** It is made from pancreas. The pancreas produces insulin. The glucose is in the blood. When pancreas detects a lot of glucose in the blood, it releases insulin into the blood. Then, insulin opens the cells, so glucose can go inside and the cells can get energy.

Noted:

- Original script
- Elaboration= introducion= signalling
- Elaboration to suport understanding
- Elaboration= repetition for emphasis

Figure 2. The script of *How the human body gets energy*.

The script of Video 3 Common symptoms of diabetes

New script rearranged during the co-design activity

The signing that you are going to see now is about if you have diabetes. What are the symptoms in your life if you have diabetes? If you have diabetes and you ignore it, what's going to happen? **Now if you have diabetes, but you don't know that you have diabetes...** it's important that if these things in your life are the same in the list I am going to talk about now. **You should get yourself tested by the doctor.** If in your life, you feel regularly tired, don't have any energy; **you just want to sit around.** Or if your eyesight is getting worse; you can't see very well. Or **if you eat proper, and you eat well, you eat regularly also, but you don't gain weight,** you keep losing weight, you stay thin. **You are eating well, you shouldn't be thin, but you are!** Or you regularly go to the toilet. **Or if you drink some water, but you still feel thirsty. You drink some more, but you still feel thirsty;** you keep feeling thirsty. Or, maybe, in your genital area, you have an itching that is not going away. Or there just no interest in sex. Perhaps there's an erectile problem. Or for women, you don't feel interested in sex. Or if you have a wound, you cut yourself, for example. You clean it and you put a plaster on, but it doesn't heal, it just stays as a wound. **So if you have these things that I just mentioned, you may possibly have diabetes. You have to go to the doctor for a test to make sure. You have to!** If you keep ignoring these symptoms, the consequence can be very dangerous. If you keep on living and you just ignore it, you could become blind. Or you could get a stroke. You could get a heart attack. Or you could have kidney failure when your kidney doesn't work anymore. Or where you had a wound, it does not heal. Infection grows; they have to amputate it. **So all of these things could happen. If you think, perhaps, I have diabetes, it doesn't matter... You can't do that, you can die! You have to go to the doctor. The doctor can explain how the treatment works. And you can follow the advice.**

Noted:

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| Original script | Simplification of the terms: "lethargic," "genital thrush," and "Impotent" |
| Elaboration to support understanding | Elaboration= repetition for emphasis |

Figure 3. The script of *Common symptoms for diabetes*.

The script of Video 4 Why people become diabetic

New script rearranged during the co-design activity

Diabetes and energy, all of these, we have given you information. But now if you have diabetes, did the person who coughed has given me diabetes? No! That is not possible. If there was another person who was sick with a cold, a cough, or anything like that? No, it can't be transferred like that. Diabetes comes from your own lifestyle. It is your responsibility to live a healthy life. If you don't care about what you eat, don't care about exercise, don't care about you smoking, you drink, you don't care! Then, you can develop diabetes.

If you are 35 years old or older, anything older than 35, you have to be careful because your body is getting older. Your pancreas is working very hard and getting old. So you have to be careful the older you get. Be extra careful. Exercise often. And do healthy things. It is very important.

If your mother and father, your parents, if they have diabetes, it means that you have to be careful. Be extra careful because you may develop diabetes. If your parents have diabetes, we have seen that their children who grew up,... if they don't live a healthy lifestyle, they developed diabetes. If you exercise and stay healthy, that is good. But if you don't, and your parents have diabetes, it means that you can develop diabetes yourself. So it's important that you eat well, exercise, and be healthy.

In your family, if there are Indians, or perhaps you are an Indian, or your parents are Indians, or your grandparents are Indians, you have to be careful. That means you could develop diabetes. It is because Indians were born with the body that tends to develop diabetes easily, more certain than others. So if you are Indian descendant, you have to be careful about what you eat and live a healthy life.

If a woman is pregnant and gives birth to a baby, and the baby is very big and heavy, the baby weighs 4-5 kg,... the reason for a big baby could be the mother did not have enough insulin. And that means there was too much glucose in the mother that causes the baby to gain a lot of weight. Once the baby is born, and it is a big baby, then the mother could probably produce insulin normal again. But you still have to remember to eat healthily and exercise.

Maybe you have cholesterol. What is it? You know those yellow things in your blood. They stick to the side of your veins. That cause blockage when they grow thicker. So if you have a lot of that in your blood, you have to be careful about what you eat and be healthy, be active, walk around... because you can develop diabetes.

Perhaps, you have high blood pressure. Are you aware of what blood pressure is? If you go to the doctor and they test your blood pressure, and they tell you that you have high blood pressure, that is dangerous. So then you must know that you can develop diabetes. So if you have high blood pressure, you need to be careful and live a healthy lifestyle. Eat good and correct food and exercise. It is the same if you have heart disease. If you have any issue with your heart, you have to be careful because you can develop diabetes. You have to be careful, you have to live a healthy life and exercise.

A person who is very overweight, that person has to be very careful because he or she can develop diabetes. The reason for that is there are a lot of cells in your body, and the insulin has to open the cells for glucose to open the cells. But if you are overweight, there is a layer of fat around the cells, and the insulin struggles to open the cells for glucose. And that is when you can develop diabetes. So if you are overweight, you have to be very careful. Try to be healthy, eat well. It's very important.

If the person is just sitting around, not walking around, not going for a jog, or any sport, nothing, just sitting around, that person can develop diabetes. Because that is not healthy. You have to be more active and do more exercise.

Perhaps a person is not eating very healthily. He is a lot of burgers, pizzas, a lot of chips, a lot of sweets, drinking carbonated cool drinks, ice cream, all of these kinds of food, not eating healthily, not eating fruits or vegetables, or, perhaps, just a little bit of those. That person can develop diabetes. You have to be careful. It's fine if you eat some fast food, but at the same time, you have to eat good balanced diet.

Now if you look at your own life, and you question whether or not you are healthy. Look at the thing we previously mentioned. If you are older than 35, if you are overweight, if your parents have diabetes... look through of these things, and you think, ok, I am, I am, I am, etc., that means you may have diabetes, you have to go to doctor to test it. You have to do that. It's better for you to be healthy. So if you go to that list and you say these things don't apply, then you have to keep on living a healthy lifestyle. That is important.

There is a list that you can look at. If you see something that is in your life that happens with you, then you tap that. Go through the list. If there is something that is not relevant to you, do not tap that!

Noted:

- Original script
- Elaboration= introduction= signalling
- Elaboration to support understanding
- Elaboration= repetition for emphasis
- Simplification of a term: "inactive"

Figure 4. The script of *Why people become diabetic*.

The script of Video 5 Brief information about treatment and self-management

New script rearranged during the co-design activity

When you have diabetes and you meet a doctor, and the doctor tells you, explains what you should do, it is important that you understand them completely. **Don't just pretend that you understand.** The doctor is going to explain to you, perhaps give you some pills or injections, or explain how you should eat, what you should not eat, and exercise. **It's important that you understand and do the things that the doctor tells you to do.** **Because you have a pancreas that doesn't give you enough insulin, so the glucose level arises. But if you follow the doctor's advice, there can be balance between insulin and glucose.** You can live a healthy life and a long life.

Noted:

■ Original script

■ Elaboration to support understanding ■ Elaboration= repetition for emphasis

Figure 5 The script of *Brief information about treatment and self-management*.